

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DNA METHYLATION IS AN EPIGENETIC BIOMARKER OF AGING

Desyatova M.,

Senior Lecturer,

Ural State Medical University, Yekaterinburg, Russia,

Ponomarev A.,

candidate of medical sciences, associate professor,

Ural State Medical University, Yekaterinburg, Russia, Institute of Medical Cell Technology, Yekaterinburg,

Russia

Korotkov A.,

candidate of medical sciences, associate professor,

Ural State Medical University, Yekaterinburg, Russia, Institute of Medical Cell Technology, Yekaterinburg,

Russia

Makeyev O.

doctor of medical sciences, professor, Ural State Medical University, Yekaterinburg, Russia, Institute of

Medical Cell Technology, Yekaterinburg, Russia

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7418287>

Abstract

Introduction. Recently, epigenetic markers of aging have become a necessity and their identification is a major goal of gerontology. They can be thought of as measures of ageing at the individual level that capture inter-individual differences in the timing of onset, functional decline and death over the life course.

The aim of the study is to show the role of DNA methylation in the aging process of the body.

Materials and methods. A study algorithm has been developed to assess the biological (true) status of a patient. The method is based on the determination of DNA methylation levels.

Results and discussion. A detailed assessment of DNA methylation levels can reveal unique insights into the aging process itself, as well as act as a biomarker of biological age and inform age-related risk of common diseases. Identifying and understanding the epigenetic changes that occur during aging will help in deciphering certain aspects of physiology and pathology, and opens up prospects for developing new therapeutic approaches for selective methylome editing.

Conclusions. Aging of the human body is accompanied by an increase in DNA methylation. The study of the methylation profile can serve as an indicator of biological age and a prognostic indicator of the survival time of a particular individual.

Keywords: aging, epigenetics, chromatin, reprogramming, DNA methylation

INTRODUCTION. Recently the need for epigenetic markers of aging has emerged and their identification is a major goal of gerontology. They can be regarded as measures of aging at the individual level which record interindividual differences in the timing of onset, functional decline and death over the life course.

The aim of the study is to demonstrate the role of DNA methylation in the aging process.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. A research algorithm has been developed to estimate the biological (true) status of a patient. The method is based on determination of DNA methylation level.

Total RNA was isolated from biological samples of patients. Amplification and reverse transcription were performed, and then single-stranded cDNA was obtained. Then the detection of synthesis products was performed. The samples of five patients were analyzed: patient №1 born in 1998; patient №2 born in 1957; patient №3 born in 1943; patient №4 born in 1998; patient №5 born in 1978.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Methylation of DNA is an epigenetic control of the implementation of

genetic information in the cell [1]. It is a reversible covalent modification of DNA, where the nucleotide sequence is not changed and its coding capacity is not affected. The principle consists in the transfer of CH₃-group to cytosine at CpG-position C5 of cytosine ring to form 5-methylcytosine, which increases the DNA helix pitch and its hydrophobicity [2]. It promotes more active interaction of proteins with corresponding DNA sites - chromatin condensation, which prevents the attachment of activating transcription factors to their targets on DNA and architectural proteins, establishing promoter-enhancer interactions, as well as the stimulation of heterochromatin formation. In this way, reading information is inhibited.

Methylation is one of the permissible chemical modifications of DNA in vertebrates, which is stably maintained in a series of cell divisions. It occurs thanks to a whole family of DNA methyltransferases. Two types of normal methylation processes have been described in eukaryotic cells. Development in mammals is entirely dependent on DNA methylation, and a functional portion of the genome involved in the initial stages of development is functionally repressed at a

constant level. However, this process continues thereafter, underlying age-related changes (formation of permanent teeth, formation of secondary sexual characteristics, etc.). There is a general demethylation of the genetic material before blastocyst formation begins. During implantation, the zygote is methylated de novo. DNA methylation at the embryogenesis level is responsible for cell and tissue formation. During this process, promoter methylation occurs leading to the blockade of "non-functional" genes as the growing organism matures [3]. This process is carried out mainly by the enzymes DNMT3A and DNMT3B and is responsible for redistribution of methylation during embryogenesis and differentiation processes in both growing and adult organisms. In turn, the methyltransferase DNMT3L is responsible for binding the above methyltransferases to S-adenosyl-L-methionine, which is the source of methyl groups for DNA. The second type of methylation activity is 'maintenance' methylation in the DNA daughter chain formed during replication (DNMT1). In this way, the already existing methylation pattern, i.e. the structure inherent to the parent chain, is maintained.

It has been observed that the development of various pathological conditions is accompanied by changes in the epigenetic landscape. Changes in DNA methylation in a number of cancers, cardiovascular diseases and aging are examples. Epigenetic regulation of gene activity, which is based on abnormal methylation of CpG islands in promoter regions leading to their complete inactivation, plays a major role.

DNA methylation profile changes throughout life. Methylation of many genes increases with age in humans. In particular, epigenetic changes have been shown to occur in ageing organisms. They occur at various levels, including chemical modification of histones and gene promoters and enhancers. The ultimate result of epigenetic transformations during aging is a change in the local availability of genetic material, the consequences of which are erroneous gene expression, reactivation of transposable elements, and genomic instability [4].

Figure 1. Dependence of biological age on calendar age
Result of PAGE electrophoresis of patients' DNA.

From left to right: DNA marker - DNA low range ladder 25-700 bp; 1 - DNA of patient born in 1960 (№5); 2 - DNA of patient born in 1957 (№4); 3 - DNA of patient born in 1943 (№3); 4 - DNA of patient born in 1998 (№1); 5 - DNA of patient born in 1978 (№2)

Figure 1 represents the results of the PCR assay. Particular attention is paid to the high telomerase expression in the amplification of samples 4 and 5. The results indicate that these patients 1 and 2 have high telomerase activity, indicating a reduced rate of aging.

It is thought that changes in DNA methylation have a significant effect on the rate of aging through the regulation of genes susceptible to age-related diseases. [5] For example, aging is also manifested by endothelial dysfunction and decreased elasticity of blood vessels in one of the common chronic diseases, atherosclerosis. During vascular aging, oxidative stress is increased under the influence of DNA methylation. In particular, endothelial NO synthase (eNOS) expression is specific to endothelial cells and NO synthesis and regulation of vascular function occurs [6]. The promoter region of NOS3 gene, which codes for eNOS, is hypomethylated under physiological conditions but is

highly methylated under pathological conditions resulting in decreased expression of NOS3 gene and NO production.

CONCLUSIONS:

1. Aging in human organism is accompanied by increased methylation of DNA.
2. The study of methylation profile (methylated and unmethylated genes) can serve as an indicator of biological age and a prognostic indicator of the survival time of a particular individual.

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